

Combined Heat and Power (CHP): Technical Performance, Environmental Impact, and Integration in District Heating Systems

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Combined Heat & Power CHP & Cogeneration

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Abstract

Combined Heat and Power (CHP), also known as cogeneration, is an energy-efficient technology that simultaneously produces electricity and useful thermal energy from a single fuel source. Unlike conventional systems that reject a significant portion of fuel energy as waste heat, CHP systems recover and utilize this thermal energy, thereby improving overall fuel utilization. This article evaluates the thermodynamic working principle, technical performance, environmental impact, and integration of CHP within district heating networks. A simplified numerical example demonstrates that CHP systems can achieve total efficiencies above 80% and reduce primary energy consumption by approximately 30% compared to separate generations. The findings confirm that properly designed and optimized CHP systems represent a technically viable and environmentally beneficial solution for modern energy systems.

Keywords: Combined Heat and Power (CHP), Cogeneration, Energy Efficiency, District Heating Systems, Primary Energy Savings, Emission Reduction.

1. Introduction

One of the most effective strategies for reducing fuel consumption and mitigating greenhouse gas emissions is Improving energy efficiency. Conventional electricity generation systems can only produce electricity, while the remaining energy is rejected as waste heat. This system reduces overall efficiency and increases environmental impact also.

Combined Heat and Power (CHP) systems address this inefficiency by simultaneously producing electricity and useful heat from a single fuel source. By recovering waste heat and utilizing it for industrial processes, space heating, or district heating applications, CHP systems significantly improve total fuel utilization (Dincer & Rosen, 2013).

CHP technology is particularly suitable for applications where both electricity and thermal energy are required. Furthermore, its environmental performance depends on fuel type, technology configuration, and operating strategy (Bianchi & De Pascale, 2012; Evans, 1993).

This article's purpose is to evaluate technical and environmental performance of CHP systems compared to conventional separate heat and power production, with emphasis on thermodynamic efficiency, district heating system, and emission characteristics.

Working Principle of CHP Systems

Combined Heat and Power (CHP), or cogeneration technology simultaneously produces electricity and useful thermal energy from using a single fuel source. Unlike conventional power generation systems—where a large portion of the fuel energy is rejected as waste heat—CHP systems recover and utilize this thermal energy for practical applications such as space heating, domestic hot water, industrial processes, or district heating networks (Dincer & Rosen, 2013).

A CHP system consists of a prime mover (such as a gas turbine, steam turbine, or reciprocating engine), an electrical generator, and a heat recovery unit. Fuel is supplied to the prime mover (turbine), where chemical energy is converted into

mechanical energy. Mechanical energy drives an electrical generator to produce electricity. During this process, a significant amount of thermal energy remains in the exhaust gases or cooling systems. Instead of being discharged to the environment, this heat is captured through heat recovery units and delivered as useful thermal output (Chamra & Mago, 2008).

Figure 1. Simplified schematic of a CHP system (Author's illustration).

The overall energy efficiency of a CHP system is defined as:

$$\eta_{tot}^{CHP} = \frac{\dot{W} + \dot{Q}_H}{\dot{E}_f}$$

where:

- \dot{W} = electrical power output
- \dot{Q}_H = useful heat output
- \dot{E}_f = fuel energy input rate

where \dot{W} represents the electrical power output, \dot{Q}_H is the useful heat output, and \dot{E}_f is the fuel energy input rate. (Dincer & Rosen, 2013; Chamra & Mago, 2008).

Technical Performance Example

For illustrative purposes, representative efficiency values typical of gas-fired CHP systems are assumed.

To evaluate the thermodynamic advantage of cogeneration, a simplified steady-state example is considered. Assume a CHP system operating with a fuel energy input rate of

$$\dot{E}_f = 100 \text{ MW}$$

The system produces:

- Electrical power output: $\dot{W} = 38 \text{ MW}$
- Useful thermal output: $\dot{Q}_H = 45 \text{ MW}$

According to the first-law definition of total CHP efficiency (Dincer & Rosen, 2013),

$$\eta_{tot}^{CHP} = \frac{\dot{W} + \dot{Q}_H}{\dot{E}_f}$$

Substituting the values given:

$$\eta_{tot}^{CHP} = \frac{38 + 45}{100} = 0.83$$

$$\eta_{tot}^{CHP} = 83\%$$

Thus, 83% of the fuel energy is converted into useful outputs, while only 17% is lost as waste heat or irreversibility.

Comparison with Separate Production

If the same electricity (38 MW) were generated in a conventional power plant with 40% efficiency:

$$Fuel_{electricity} = \frac{38}{0.40} = 95 \text{ MW}$$

If the same heat (45 MW) were produced in a boiler operating at 90% efficiency:

$$Fuel_{heat} = \frac{45}{0.90} = 50 \text{ MW}$$

Total fuel required in separate production:

$$95 + 50 = 145 \text{ MW}$$

Primary energy saving due to CHP:

$$\frac{145 - 100}{145} \times 100 \approx 31\%$$

Figure 2. Comparison of fuel consumption between CHP and separate heat and power production.

This analysis shows that cogeneration significantly improves overall fuel utilization compared to separate generation systems. From an energy perspective, the integration of heat recovery reduces fuel demand and associated emissions, consistent with thermodynamic performance principles discussed by Dincer and Rosen (2013).

CHP in District Heating Systems

The integration of Combined Heat and Power (CHP) systems with District Heating Networks (DHN) enables higher primary energy utilization compared to separate electricity and heat production. A district heating network distributes thermal energy from centralized or distributed CHP units to multiple buildings through insulated pipelines, allowing simultaneous generation and delivery of electricity and useful heat (Franco et al., 2017).

A key design parameter in CHP-DHN systems is the cogeneration ratio (λ), defined as the ratio between thermal and electrical power produced. Different technologies such as steam turbines, gas turbines, and internal combustion engines exhibit different λ values, influencing their suitability for district applications (Franco et al., 2017).

Recent developments in 4th generation district heating highlight distributed generation and energy reciprocity among buildings. Optimization studies show that it can reduce total annualized cost by up to 25%-40% the coordinated heat and electricity exchange and lower CO₂ emissions compared to conventional centralized systems (Sameti & Haghghat, 2019).

Overall, CHP integrated with district heating enhances system efficiency, reduces emissions, and improves operational flexibility when properly sized and optimized.

Environmental Impact of CHP Systems

CHP or cogeneration is beneficial for environmental because it produces electricity and useful heat simultaneously from the same fuel, for this reason it's reducing primary energy consumption—leading to lower CO₂ emissions. However, it is crucial to differentiate between local and global effects to accurately assess the environmental advantages of CHP. CO₂ primarily contributes to global climate change, whereas pollutants such as NO_x and CO mainly affect local air quality and have a more localized environmental impact (Bianchi & De Pascale, 2012).

According to Evans (1993), if 10% of national electricity demand is met by small-scale CHP, CO₂ emissions could decrease by about 4% and SO₂ by up to 12%, mainly due to the replacement of coal-fired power plants with natural gas-based cogeneration. However, CHP is not emission-free. It still emits pollutants such as NO_x, CO, and CO₂, depending on the prime mover (e.g., internal combustion engine or micro gas turbine).

Small-scale CHP technologies demonstrate varying emission characteristics depending on engine type and air–fuel ratio. Lean-burn engines and gas turbines significantly reduce CO emissions compared to conventional spark-ignition engines, although NO_x levels may vary (Evans, 1993).

Table: Emission Comparison (g/kWh of useful output)

Source: Evans (1993)

Pollutant	Coal Power Plant	Gas Boiler	CHP (Conventional Engine)	CHP (Lean Burn / Gas Turbine)
CO ₂	1120	228	—	—
NO _x	5.5	0.23	10–16	2.7
CO	0.15	0.06	37–60	0.7–4.0
HC/NMVOC	0.02	0.0015	2.0–2.3	0.3–1.3

Overall, CHP systems reduce CO₂ emission for using less fuel and improved efficiency, while local pollutant performance depends on technology configuration and operational control (Evans, 1993).

Challenges and Future Outlook

Heat-demand variability is the key challenge for CHP in district heating. Due to the change of the residential and commercial load by season and time of day it can reduce CHP operating hours and often requires auxiliary boilers to cover peak demand. This may lower the effective cogeneration share if the CHP plant is not properly sized and dispatched (Franco et al., 2017).

A related issue is sizing and operational strategy: over-sizing can lead to inefficient part-load operation, while under-sizing increases reliance on backup heat sources. The literature therefore emphasizes multi-level approaches that jointly consider design, sizing, and operation (Franco et al., 2017).

From an environmental perspective, CHP benefits are clear for CO₂ due to fuel savings, but outcomes for local pollutants (e.g., NO_x and CO) depend on technology

type, operating conditions, and the chosen reference method used to quantify “savings” (Bianchi & De Pascale, 2012).

Looking ahead, “4th generation” district energy concepts highlight distributed CHP and energy reciprocity among buildings (heat and electricity exchange), where optimization-based coordination can reduce total annualized cost and emissions compared to conventional centralized operation (Sameti & Haghghat, 2019).

7. Conclusion

This study evaluated the working principle, technical performance, environmental impact, and district heating integration of CHP technology. Based on first-law efficiency analysis, CHP systems can achieve total efficiencies exceeding 80% and reduce primary energy consumption by approximately 30% compared to separate production (Dincer & Rosen, 2013).

When integrated with district heating networks and optimized operational strategies, CHP can reduce greenhouse gas emission and improve system-level efficiency. But technology configuration is a factor in local pollutants’ performance. Overall, findings in modern energy systems confirm that CHP represents a thermodynamically efficient and environmentally strategic solution.

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